

Infographic biodiversity interdependencies of SDGs (D3.6)

January, 2025

Authors:

Audra Balundė, Goda Kaniušonytė, Aistė Bakaitytė-Bagdonė (MRU)

Katarina Haugen (UGOT)

Liam Ó Riada, Julia Neidig (BC3)

Mara van Welie (ESCI)

Rosalie van Dam (WR)

Funded by
the European Union

Technical References

Project Acronym	BIOTraCes
Project Title	BIOdiversity and Transformative Change for plural and nature positive societies
Project Coordinator	Rosalie van Dam (WR)
Project Duration	2022 – 2026 (4 years)

Deliverable No.	D 3.6
Dissemination level¹	PU
Work Package	WP3 Strategies and Approaches for Just Transformative Changes
Task	Task 3.5 Biodiversity interdependencies of SDGs
Lead beneficiary	MRU
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	UGOT, CER, BC3, UBB, WR, ESCI
Due date of deliverable	31 st January 2025
Actual submission date	31 st January 2025

1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
V0.1	24 th January 2025	MRU ESCI	Audra Balundè, Mara van Welie
V0.2	28 th January 2025	MRU ESCI	Audra Balundè
V0.3	29 th January 2025	MRU ESCI WR	Audra Balundè, Katarina Haugen, Liam Ó Riada, Rosalie van Dam
V1	30 th January 2025	MRU WR ESCI	Audra Balundè, Rosalie van Dam Mara van Welie

Infographics

Biodiversity Interdependencies of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Local experiences across Europe show biodiversity is key in achieving all SDGs

The infographics presented in this deliverable are based on a policy brief, which highlights the key lessons learned and includes the recommendations outlined here:

Lessons Learned From How SDGs Are Implemented and Experienced in Local and Diverse Contexts

1. SDGs take on unique meanings in different cases and contexts.
2. Non-human entities (i.e. various forms of biodiversity) are rarely seen as primary beneficiaries of achieved SDGs.
3. Biodiversity and secured ecosystem services are important in achieving SDGs; however, the terms 'ecosystem services' and 'SDGs' are problematic. The former may be seen as 'exploiting' biodiversity, while the latter overlooks marginalized communities.
4. Biodiversity is interdependent with non-biodiversity-related SDGs across cases; however, inequalities and imbalance between human activities and ecosystems compromise this relationship.
5. Despite their benefits, SDGs are seen as abstract and disconnected from local social, environmental and political practices, which complicates their application. SDGs' focus on reconciling economic growth with environmental sustainability is seen as contradictory and insufficient to foster systemic transformation. The SDGs are criticized for lacking empowerment initiatives and being disconnected from everyday discourse.

Recommendations for Policy

1. Tailor SDG implementation strategies to local contexts and acknowledge that the interpretation and relevance of SDGs vary. Promote SDGs' flexibility and alignment with local needs and priorities.
2. Recognize and integrate the role of non-human entities as key beneficiaries to promote holistic and sustainable outcomes of SDGs. Encourage policies that prioritize ecosystems alongside human development, without prioritizing the latter.
3. Look for inclusive ways to define ecosystem services. Promote a focus within the SDGs on the empowerment of marginalized communities.
4. Promote policies that recognize the interdependence between biodiversity recovery and non-biodiversity-related SDGs. Focus on reducing inequalities and fostering balanced relationships between human activities and ecosystems.
5. Develop publicly accessible guidelines and practical tools to translate SDGs into tangible, actionable steps tailored to local contexts and marginalized communities. Reconceptualize the SDG framework by transparently addressing its colonial and capitalist roots and limitations (e.g. growth-centric and Global North-centric focus and neglect of underrepresented populations). Ensure that intersectionalities, such as gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status are considered to address overlapping challenges and barriers. Incorporate measures to make biodiversity-relevant SDGs relatable to enhance public understanding and engagement.

Unfolding of SDGs in Different Contexts

The longer the ray, the higher the importance attributed to SDG.

Sustainable Development Goals

- | | | | |
|--|--------------------------------|--|---|
| | 1 - No Poverty | | 7 - Affordable and Clean Energy |
| | 2 - Zero Hunger | | 8 - Decent Work and Economic Growth |
| | 3 - Good Health and Well-Being | | 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure |
| | 4 - Quality Education | | 10 - Reduced Inequalities |
| | 5 - Gender Equality | | 11 - Sustainable Cities and Communities |
| | 6 - Clean Water and Sanitation | | 12 - Responsible Consumption and Production |
| | | | 13 - Climate Action |
| | | | 14 - Life Below Water |
| | | | 15 - Life on Land |
| | | | 16 - Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions |
| | | | 17 - Partnerships for the Goals |

Relevance of SDGs for Local Biodiversity Innovation Contexts

Understanding the Concept of SDGs:

Relevance of SDGs to the Local Biodiversity Innovations:

Local Stakeholders Mentioning SDGs:

Local Biodiversity Innovations

- | | | |
|--|--|---|
| Foodpark against Industry
Urbanisation The Netherlands | Mértola Future Lab
Agriculture and Food Portugal | Urban Schoolyards - Biodiversity Lab
Urbanisation Spain |
| High Nature Value Farming
Agriculture and food Romania | Bottom-up Forest Biodiversity
Forestry Sweden | Social Opportunities in Ecological Recovery
Maritime Living Sources Lithuania |
| Fluvial Eco-Partnership
Maritime Living Sources Italy | Traditional Herders' Knowledge
Forestry Hungary | Nature-Inclusive Building
Urbanisation The Netherlands |

Beneficiaries of SDGs: Non-human vs. Anthropic Bias

Non-human entities are less frequently recognized as primary beneficiaries of achieved SDGs.

Non-human Entities Emerging as Key Beneficiaries of SDGs in the Local Biodiversity Innovations:

Local People Emerging as Key Beneficiaries of Ecosystem Services and Improved Biodiversity:

Local Biodiversity Innovations

- | | | |
|--|--|---|
| Foodpark against Industry
Urbanisation The Netherlands | Mértola Future Lab
Agriculture and Food Portugal | Urban Schoolyards - Biodiversity Lab
Urbanisation Spain |
| High Nature Value Farming
Agriculture and food Romania | Bottom-up Forest Biodiversity
Forestry Sweden | Social Opportunities in Ecological Recovery
Maritime Living Sources Lithuania |
| Fluvial Eco-Partnership
Maritime Living Sources Italy | Traditional Herders' Knowledge
Forestry Hungary | Nature-Inclusive Building
Urbanisation The Netherlands |